

**FUNDAMENTALS OF DEVELOPING FIRST AID SKILLS
IN STUDENTS: A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS.**

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The article examines the theoretical foundations of developing first aid skills in students of non-medical higher education institutions. An analysis of existing approaches to first aid training is conducted, key problems of educational programs are identified, including insufficient theoretical training, lack of practical classes and low motivation of students. The need to integrate innovative methods, such as simulation training, interactive multimedia technologies and role-playing scenarios, is substantiated to improve the effectiveness of training. The authors emphasize the importance of developing a first aid culture as an important component of public safety and social responsibility. Conclusions are made about the need for a comprehensive revision of training programs with an emphasis on the balance of theoretical and practical training.

INTRODUCTION. The relevance of the research topic is determined by the importance of developing first aid skills in students of non-medical universities. In the context of modern reality, when emergencies, accidents and sudden conditions require immediate

intervention, knowledge of first aid algorithms becomes a necessary element of the general safety culture of society. According to statistics from the World Health Organization, up to 60% of fatalities could be prevented if the victim had received first aid in a timely manner [1]. However, an analysis of educational programs shows that first aid training in non-medical educational institutions remains insufficiently structured and organized, which reduces students' readiness to effectively respond to emergency situations [2; pp. 184-192].

Modern approaches to first aid training are focused not only on the transfer of theoretical knowledge, but also on the development of practical skills that allow students to act confidently under stress. However, the existing training system in non-medical universities is characterized by a number of problems: insufficient hours allocated to studying first aid, a shortage of qualified teachers, weak student motivation and limited use of modern educational technologies [3]. Many programs are focused primarily on the theoretical aspect, which leads to low training efficiency, since without practical training, students feel unsure when providing assistance in real life [4].

Another problem is the lack of a comprehensive approach to first aid training. Including basic courses in university programs is an important step, but their content is often limited to general information, which does not allow students to fully master the algorithms for providing assistance. In addition, first aid teaching in most cases is not accompanied by mandatory practical exams, which reduces the level of students' training and their readiness to act in extreme conditions [5].

In view of the above, it is necessary to revise educational approaches, including strengthening practical training, integrating interactive methods, using simulation training and role-playing scenarios. Such technologies allow trainees not only to memorize algorithms for providing assistance, but also to develop confidence in their actions, reducing the level of anxiety in emergency situations [2; pp. 184-192].

The aim of the study is to conduct a theoretical analysis of existing approaches to teaching first aid to students of non-medical universities and to identify key problems in this area. The following tasks were set within the framework of the work: to analyze the theoretical foundations of first aid and its importance in the education system; to study the existing methods of teaching first aid skills in non-medical universities; to identify the main problems associated with the deficiencies in theoretical and practical training of students; to justify the need to introduce innovative teaching methods aimed at improving the effectiveness of preparing students to provide first aid. The object of the study is the process of developing first aid skills in students of non-medical universities, and the subject is

modern educational approaches to teaching first aid, their effectiveness and prospects for improvement. The scientific novelty of the work lies in a comprehensive analysis of the existing first aid training system and proposing effective methods for its improvement with an emphasis on practical training and the use of modern teaching technologies. Thus, consideration of this topic is relevant and in demand in light of the need to improve the level of public safety and the readiness of citizens to provide emergency care in critical situations.

Materials and methods

The study is based on the analysis of modern approaches to teaching first aid skills to students of non-medical higher education institutions. The work included a theoretical analysis of scientific literature, regulatory documents and educational programs aimed at developing competencies in this area. The main focus is on reviewing existing teaching methods, assessing their effectiveness and identifying shortcomings in the educational systems of different countries, including the practice of higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The study uses data on the historical evolution of first aid, from the activities of medieval monastic orders to modern educational standards, including the use of simulation technologies and interactive teaching methods [6]. The main protocols for providing assistance, such as BLS (basic life support) and CPR (cardiopulmonary resuscitation), as well as their adaptation in educational programs for students of non-medical specialties are considered [7].

The existing educational systems in higher education institutions were analyzed, key problems were identified, including a lack of theoretical training, a limited number of practical classes and a low level of student motivation [8]. The impact of the shortage of academic hours allocated to mastering first aid on the level of training of students was assessed [2; pp. 184-192]. The methodology of teaching first aid was also studied, taking into account the use of modern educational technologies, such as virtual reality, multimedia simulators and role-playing scenarios, ensuring more effective acquisition of theoretical knowledge and development of practical skills [4].

In addition, an analysis of regulatory documents governing the teaching of first aid in universities of Uzbekistan was conducted, with an emphasis on the integration of relevant courses into educational programs. Changes made to the curricula since 2000, including the introduction of disciplines related to health protection, as well as their practical application in the training of students were considered [5].

Particular attention is paid to assessing students' motivation for learning first aid. The studies indicate a low level of awareness of the importance of this knowledge among students of non-medical universities, which is due to the lack of integration of the topic into the main disciplines and the lack of practical classes [10]. Methods for increasing motivation are considered, including the introduction of practical exams, participation in volunteer programs and the use of real cases demonstrating the importance of timely assistance [3].

Results

An analysis of existing approaches to teaching first aid in non-medical higher education institutions has revealed a number of key problems associated with the development of emergency care skills in students. The main problem is the insufficient theoretical justification of the learning process, which leads to fragmented acquisition of knowledge and the lack of a holistic understanding of algorithms for action in critical situations [8]. Modern educational programs are focused primarily on independent study of theoretical material, which significantly limits students' opportunities to consolidate the knowledge they have acquired in practice [9, pp. 526–528].

Historical analysis has shown that first aid as a structured discipline began to develop in the second half of the 19th century, but its integration into the educational programs of non-medical universities has not yet reached the required level. In modern conditions, the emphasis in first aid training is shifting towards interactive and simulation methods, but their implementation in the educational process remains insufficient [2, pp. 184–192]. In this regard, students experience a deficit of practical skills, which affects their confidence in their own actions in real emergency situations [3].

An analysis of educational programs of non-medical universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan showed that the discipline "Fundamentals of Medical Knowledge" occupies only an insignificant place in the structure of students' training. For example, within the framework of the correspondence form of study in the direction of "Primary Education" at the Urgench State University, 120 hours are allocated for this course, of which only 24 are allocated for classroom studies, and 96 hours are allocated for independent work [2, pp. 184-192]. This leads to the fact that most students do not receive a sufficient number of practical classes necessary for developing automaticity of actions under stress.

One of the main reasons for the low level of training is the insufficient connection between the theoretical and practical aspects of training. Even with basic theoretical knowledge, students face difficulties in applying it in practice, which indicates the need to

develop new teaching methods [4]. The introduction of modern technologies such as virtual reality (VR), interactive multimedia courses and simulators contributes to more effective assimilation of material, but their use remains fragmented [2, pp. 184–192].

In addition, a low level of student motivation to study first aid has been identified, which is due to the insufficient integration of this topic into general educational programs. A study conducted at one of the universities in Taif (Saudi Arabia) found that only 14% of students in non-medical specialties receive adequate training in first aid, which confirms the existing gaps in the educational system [10]. Similar results were obtained at Yarmouk University (Jordan), where a shortage of both theoretical and practical classes in first aid was noted, which reduces the level of students' readiness to act in extreme situations [11].

Problems in the organization of the educational process related to the lack of a comprehensive approach to the formation of a first aid culture have also been identified. According to the World Health Organization, up to 60% of fatal cases could be prevented if the people around had basic skills in providing emergency aid [1]. However, current educational programs do not provide the required level of training, as they are limited to studying general safety issues and do not provide for in-depth mastery of algorithms for actions in critical situations [5].

Thus, the analysis showed that the effectiveness of first aid training in non-medical universities remains low due to insufficient theoretical training, lack of practical classes, weak student motivation and lack of integration of modern educational technologies. To improve the situation, it is necessary to revise the curricula with an increase in hours for practical training, introduce innovative teaching methods such as simulation training and role-playing scenarios, and develop new methodological approaches aimed at increasing students' awareness and responsibility.

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